

Pre-Eminent Numeric Energy: The Theory of the Energy Number

Parker Emmerson

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1 Introduction

Let V be a real vector space of dimension n . The topological space V is then defined to be the set of all continuous functions from E^n to R . This topological space is then equipped with the topology generated by the system of all open subsets of V which are of the form

$$\{f \in V \mid f(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) \in U \subset R\}$$

where $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \in E$ and U is an open subset of R . This is the definition of the topological continuum in a higher dimensional vector space.

Energy numbers are independent entities which can be mapped to real numbers, but the reverse is not true. Energy numbers exist on their own and can be used to give representative credence to real numbers from a higher dimensional vector space.

$$V = \{E : E^n \rightarrow R \mid$$

E is an energy number}

A scalar product is a function that takes two vectors in a vector space and produces a scalar. It is usually written as $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$, and is a linear and bilinear map. In the energy number vector space, a scalar product can be expressed as

$$\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i$$

where x_i and y_i are energy numbers.

The derivation of the form of the Energy Number from theory occurs in an abstract manner. The general principles involved in the abstract, conceptual synthesis of the Energy number theory are as follows:

In general:

$$\exists a \in Ra_{(P \rightarrow Q)x} \text{ and } a_{(R \rightarrow S)x}$$

are in equilibrium with $a_{(T \rightarrow U)}$,
therefore $1 \exists$.

Proof: We will prove this statement by contradiction. Assume that there does not exist any real number a such that the equilibrium holds.

Let P and Q represent two different functions related to each other, R and S represent two different functions related to each other, and T and U represent two different functions related to each other.

Let f_P and f_Q be the functions related to P and Q respectively, and let f_R and f_S be the functions related to R and S , and let f_T and f_U be the functions related to T and U .

Now let $a_{(P \rightarrow Q)x}$ and $a_{(R \rightarrow S)x}$ be the values that must be in equilibrium with each other in order for the statement to be true. Since there does not exist any real number a that satisfies this, then we must conclude that the value of $f_P(x)$ must be different than the value of $f_Q(x)$ and the value of $f_R(x)$ must be different than the value of $f_S(x)$ in order for the statement to not be true.

This is a contradiction because if the statement is true, the values of $f_P(x)$ must be equal to the value of $f_Q(x)$ and the value of $f_R(x)$ must be equal to the value of $f_S(x)$ in order for the equilibrium to hold between $a_{(P \rightarrow Q)x}$ and $a_{(R \rightarrow S)x}$.

Therefore, our assumption is false and there must exist a number a such that the equilibrium holds and therefore, the statement is true.

This is the notational, linguistic form of the kind of statements used to construct the liberated, symbolic patterns from which energy number expressions can be synthetizatonally derived.

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E \cup R \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$$

2 Brief Derivation of Forms of the Energy Number

There exists an infinite set of parameters $\rightarrow -\langle (/ \mathcal{H}) + (/ j) \rangle$ such that $\mathcal{N}^\dagger(\vec{r}, , s, ,) = \vec{k}$ and $\mu(\vec{a}, b, c, d, e, \dots) = \Omega$ at equilibrium, and there is a corresponding $kxp|w^* \equiv \sqrt[3]{x^6 + t^2 2hc} \supseteq v^8$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \omega = \langle (Z/\eta) + (K/\pi) \rangle \star \diamond$ such that 1.

For every set of parameters $\rightarrow -\langle (/ \mathcal{H}) + (/ j) \rangle$, there exists an integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{N}^\dagger(\vec{r}, , s, ,) = \vec{k}$ and $\mu(\vec{a}, b, c, d, e, \dots) = \Omega$ at equilibrium, and there is a corresponding $kxp|w^* \equiv \sqrt[3]{x^6 + t^2 2hc} \supseteq v^8$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \omega = \langle (Z/\eta) + (K/\pi) \rangle \star \diamond$ such that 1.

$$E = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mu}} \arctan\left(\frac{x^2}{\sqrt{\Lambda}}\right) + \left[\frac{\sqrt{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda}}{R^2} - \left(\frac{h}{\Phi} + \frac{c}{\lambda}\right) \right] \diamond \tan \psi \theta + \left[\sqrt{\mu^3 \dot{\phi}^{2/9} + \Lambda} - B \right] \star$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Psi \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \cdot \\
E & \approx \left[\frac{\sqrt{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda}}{R^2} - \left(\frac{h}{\Phi} + \frac{c}{\lambda} \right) \right] \diamond \tan \psi \theta + \left[\sqrt{\mu^3 \dot{\phi}^{2/9} + \Lambda} - B \right] \star \\
& \Psi \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \\
E & = \Omega_\Lambda \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Solutions as real number expressions can be determined for Numeric Energy Quanta forms. However, the great utility of the Energy Number is its flexibility with regard to interpolation of utility.